

VIBRATION FREQUENCY DESIGN AND STUDY OF COMPOSITE FUSELAGE STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

The influence of various physical properties of composite materials on the natural vibration frequency of the cylindrical shell is studied. On this basis, an equivalent design method is proposed, which takes the vibration frequency and node position of composite fuselage structure as the design objective. Firstly, an equivalent model for isotropic material is established aiming at resolving two typical problems about position on modal nodes and deformation frequency. Secondly, through the design of experiments, the effects of the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of the composite on the beam free vibration frequency of the cylindrical shell and correlations among these parameters and natural frequencies are discussed. Finally, genetic algorithm is used to design the composite fuselage structural layout in detail based on the equivalent stiffness model. The dynamic index of the composite fuselage and target values are within acceptable limits, which verifies the correctness of the design idea of active fuselage structural stiffness.

1 INTRODUCTION

The fuselage is one of the main components of the aircraft. Compared with the existing strength-based fuselage design method, methods of fuselage stiffness design have not been effectively applied. Stiffness is related to material, boundary conditions and shape, and the stiffness characteristics of aircraft fuselage have a crucial impact on the dynamics, flight performance and quality of aircraft. However, the complexity of the fuselage structure brings many problems to the early stage of design of aircraft stiffness design.

At present, the new generation of aerospace structures are widely used in composite materials. Due to the design ability of the composite material, the optimized design of the composite laminate increases the design space of the fuselage structure in terms of stiffness, which is also the challenge to the stiffness design. In the structural design of composite materials, there are almost countless changes in the laminating mode of composite laminates, which not only changes the elastic modulus, but also changes the Poisson's ratio. The effect on the vibration characteristics of the composite fuselage structure is unknown.

Based on the equivalent stiffness model, the composite fuselage structure is designed by dynamic equivalent method, and its dynamic characteristics are calculated and analysed.

2 EQUIVALENT STIFFNESS MODEL

2.1 Establish Equivalent Stiffness Model

A fuselage structure consisting of longerons, skin and frames is studied. The natural frequency of the fuselage structure is related to its stiffness and weight, in order to simplify the model, the longerons and skin are believed to mainly provide axial stiffness of the fuselage. The influence of the frame on the axial stiffness distribution is ignored.

It is unrealistic to optimize the detailed fuselage structure in the initial stage of design because of the particularity and complexity of the fuselage structure. In order to reduce the design cost, the equivalent model method is widely used in the early stage of design. According to the similarities and differences between the model and the real structure in terms of shape and material, the equivalent

model can be divided into equivalent beam or shell model, direct geometric model, general geometric model, etc.

For example, the equivalent beam model method simplifies fuselage and converts it into a variable section beam located at its rigid center line. The stiffness of the variable stiffness beam is matched to the fuselage structure by specifying stiffness of beam section and fuselage section. Although this method could solve many engineering problems with a relatively simple idea, the accuracy of this method is not high enough for solving the dynamic stiffness problem of the fuselage.

In this paper, the general geometric model is adopted to ensure that the mass and stiffness properties of the equivalent model and the actual structure satisfy the similar relationship. In the model, the longerons are removed and the longerons and skin are equivalent to a thin-walled cylinder with a total of 9 design cross-sections. In addition, some rings are used to simulate the frame to ensure the section stiffness. In order to realize the optimal design the bending frequency of the fuselage model structure in the two planes of XY and YZ, the cross-section shape is set to a kind of circular ring with an inner circle and an outer ellipse. The vibration frequency of the model in XY and YZ planes is designed by changing the length of the major and minor axes of the outer ellipse. The linear distribution is adopted between each section, and the shape change of the section determines the stiffness distribution of the model, so as to design the position of modal nodes. The equivalent stiffness model is shown in the Fig.1.

In the optimization, the finite element analysis of the thin-walled cylinder with parameter variations is required. In order to calculate the position of the modal nodes and guarantee the quality of the elements, it is necessary to use solid element with a dense mesh. Moreover, it need to reduce the number of elements appropriately for saving optimization time and calculation cost.

For the above reasons, the generalized equivalent stiffness reduction model is adopted. Assuming that the length of the real fuselage section is 4000mm and the length of the equivalent model is 400mm. The section size and length of the fuselage section are reduced in equal proportion to ensure calculation accuracy and mesh quality. The model structure is shown in the Fig.2.

Figure 1: Cross-Section of equivalent stiffness model.

Figure 2: Equivalent stiffness model structure.

3.2 Stiffness Conversion and Stiffness Index

The stiffness equivalent model should be consistent with the stiffness characteristics of the real structure. Since the equivalent stiffness model is somewhat smaller than the real structure, it is only necessary to ensure that the stiffness distribution of the two in the axial direction is proportional. The stiffness distribution of the equivalent model can be calculated according to the requirement of real structure stiffness.

L_R : The length of the real fuselage structure

L_M : The length of the equivalent model

ρ_R : Material density of the real fuselage structure

ρ_M : Material density of the equivalent model

E_R : The elastic modulus of the real structural materials

E_M : The elastic modulus of the equivalent model materials

$I_{Ri(x/z)}$: The i-th cross section moment of inertia of the real structure

$I_{Mi(x/z)}$: The i-th cross section moment of inertia of the equivalent model

A_{Ri} : The i-th cross section area of the real structure

A_{Mi} : The i-th cross section area of the equivalent model

f_R : The frequency of the real fuselage structure

f_M : The frequency of the equivalent model

M_{ER} : The sum of the masses of the real structure except the longerons and skin

M_{EM} : The sum of the masses of frames of the equivalent model

The frequency ratio between the equivalent stiffness model and the real fuselage structure is expressed as follows.

$$\frac{f_M}{f_R} = \sqrt{\frac{\frac{E_M I_M / L_M^3}{M_M}}{\frac{E_R I_R / L_R^3}{M_R}}} \Rightarrow \sqrt{\frac{E_R I_{Ri}}{\rho_M A_{Mi} L_M + M_{KM}}} = \sqrt{\frac{E_M I_{Mi}}{\rho_M A_{Mi} L_M + M_{KM}}} \cdot \left(\frac{L_R}{L_M}\right)^3 \cdot \frac{f_R}{f_M} \quad (1)$$

According to the formula of calculating the frequency $f = \sqrt{K/M}$, EI/L^3 could represent the simplified form of axial stiffness of the structure and M represents the total mass of the structure. The stiffness level of the real structure on each design cross-section can be calculated by using the equivalent model cross-section data and frequency ratio. Since the frequency value is related to the stiffness and mass of the structure, it could let $K_{Ri(x/z)}$ represent the stiffness level of the i-th cross-section of the real structure. Define it as follows.

$$K_{Rix} = \sqrt{\frac{E_M I_{Miy}}{\rho_M A_{Mi} L_M + M_{KM}}} \cdot \left(\frac{L_R}{L_M}\right)^3 \cdot \frac{f_R}{f_M} \quad (2)$$

$$K_{Riz} = \sqrt{\frac{E_M I_{Miz}}{\rho_M A_{Mi} L_M + M_{KM}}} \cdot \left(\frac{L_R}{L_M}\right)^3 \cdot \frac{f_R}{f_M} \quad (3)$$

Frequency F7 and F11 represent the first and second bending modal frequencies of the equivalent model in the XY plane, Frequency F8 and F10 represent the first and second bending modal frequencies of the equivalent model in the YZ plane. According to the results, the frequency values of the equivalent model are close to the target frequency values, and the positions of modal nodes are also within the constraint range. According to the conversion relationship between the equivalent stiffness model and the real fuselage structure, the $K_{Ri(x/z)}$ values are calculated as shown in the Fig.4, and the unit is mm.

Modal Frequency	F7	F8	F10	F11
Optimization Objective(cycles/time)	2100	2250	4200	4575
Optimized Result(cycles/time)	2099.9	2249.9	4204.2	4574.4

Table 1: Optimization objectives and results of modal frequency.

Modal Node	Constraint Condition (mm)	Final Result (mm)
7S1	88~92	92
7S2	308~312	308
8S1	88~92	89
8S2	308~312	312
10S1	45~50	49
10S2	198~202	200
10S3	348~352	351

11S1	45~50	50
11S2	198~202	199
11S3	348~352	348

Table 2: Constraint conditions and results of modal node position

Figure 3: Fuselage stiffness index.

3 INFLUENCE OF MATERIAL PARAMETERS ON VIBRATION OF CYLINDRICAL SHELL

The longerons and skin are believed to mainly provide axial stiffness of the fuselage, and skin can be approximated as a cylindrical shell. The above calculation of equivalent stiffness model and the stiffness index of real structure are based on isotropic materials, so the influence of anisotropic material on the beam-type vibrations is neglected. In this chapter, the influence of anisotropic material parameters on the equivalent design of composite structure is calculated, which based on the effect of anisotropic material parameters on beam-type vibrations ($n=1$) of cylindrical shell.

Figure 4: Anisotropic cylindrical shell.

The current analysis is based on the equation of motion for the free vibration of thin cylindrical shells established by Flugge. FIG. shows such an orthogonal anisotropic cylindrical shell with radius R , length L and thickness h . Assuming that the material principal axis of the cylindrical shell coincides with that of the coordinate system, the material parameters in the x, θ directions satisfy the following relationship.

$$v_x \cdot E_\theta = v_\theta \cdot E_x \quad (4)$$

Applying the classical shell theory of Flugge, the vibration equation of an orthotropic cylindrical shell is shown as follow,

$$\begin{cases} L_{11}u + L_{12}v + L_{13}w = \rho h \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} \\ L_{21}u + L_{22}v + L_{23}w = \rho h \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} \\ L_{31}u + L_{32}v + L_{33}w = \rho h \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The factors (L_{11}, L_{12} , etc.) in the above equation include tensile stiffness($D_x, D_\theta, D_{x\theta}$) and bending stiffness($K_x, K_\theta, K_{x\theta}$).

In system characteristic equation for $n = 1$, the beam-type vibration characteristics of the cylindrical shell can be obtained. In order to discuss the beam-type vibration, the result of beam theory is introduced, that is, the cylindrical shell is regarded as a free beam with radius R and thickness h . The first six modes are the translational and rotational modals in the x, y and z directions respectively. Starting from the seventh modal, the beam-type vibration frequency and the dimensionless frequency factor can be expressed as follows. I represents the moment of inertia, and A represents the cross-sectional area.

$$\omega_{beam}^2 = \frac{EI}{\rho A} \left(\frac{m\pi}{L}\right)^4 \quad \Omega_{beam}^2 = \frac{\rho R^2(1-\nu_x \cdot \nu_\theta)}{E_x} \omega_{beam}^2 \quad (6)$$

According to the above formula, it can be seen that the beam-type vibration frequency of anisotropic cylindrical shell is mainly related to the axial elastic modulus E_x and poisson's ratio. The influence of elastic modulus and poisson's ratio on the vibration frequency of cylindrical shell is analyzed below.

For modes having $n=1$, the lowest frequency corresponds to beam-type vibration of the cylindrical shell. For very long shells ($l/a > 20$) motion occurs with v and w essentially equal but of opposite sign, and thus represents a rigid body translation of the shell cross section. Simple beam theory assumes that v and w are equal for any length shell. However shell theory shows that as the shell becomes shorter the tangential displacement v becomes gradually larger than the radial displacement w up to a length-to-radius of about 5.¹

The cylindrical shell studied in this paper ($L/R=10$) is not long shell. The simple beam theory cannot be used to find the exact solution. However, the frequency relation between two approximate structures can be expressed by the factor, so the stiffness distribution is simulated by the equivalent stiffness model.

The fuselage uses T-300/5208 carbon fiber composite material with 8 layers, the material parameters are shown in the table. The stiffness matrix of carbon fiber composite laminates includes A, B and D matrices. The tensile stiffness matrix A represents the stiffness coefficient of the internal force and the mid-surface strain. The coupling stiffness matrix B represents the coupling relationship between bending and stretching. The torsional stiffness matrix D represents the stiffness coefficients related to the curvature and torsion rate of the internal torque. Due to the B matrix, the laminate has a coupling of tensile deformation and bending deformation. The bending internal force also causes in-plane deformation, and warpage occurs after the laminate is cured. Therefore, symmetrical lamination should be taken to eliminate the coupling matrix in the design.

For cylindrical shell with $L=4000, L/R=10$ and $h/R=0.01$, several kinds of lamination forms are designed, and the beam-type vibration frequencies of isotropic material and composite material are extracted by Abaqus. Then, the equivalent stiffness model and the conversion relationship are used to calculate the first-order and second-order beam-type vibration frequencies of the composite cylindrical shell. The comparison results are shown in the Tab 3. The frequency values in parentheses represent the equivalent calculation results.

Material	Al	[90°/-45°/45°/0°]s	[0°/-45°/45°/0°]s	[0°/-30°/30°/0°]s
Density (t/mm ³)	2.7e-9	1.56e-9	1.56e-9	1.56e-9
E_x (MPa)	72000	47666.71	70459.06	86425.59
E_y (MPa)	72000	47666.71	19915	10365.19
ν_x	0.33	0.3023	0.7267	1.10523
ν_y	0.33	0.3023	0.2054	0.1326
$\sqrt{1 - \nu_x \cdot \nu_\theta}$	0.94398	0.95321	0.92235	0.92382
G_{xy} (MPa)		18052	18052	14464.013

¹ Kevin Forsberg. "Axisymmetric and beam-type vibrations of thin cylindrical shells. " *AIAA Journal* 7.2(1969):221-227.

K(mm)	45.6441	48.8591	59.4027	65.7899
First order (finite element)	153.31	163.99	197.80	214.3
First order (calculate by stiffness)		164.11	199.52	220.98
Second order (finite element)	380.88	407.62	478.51	495.26
Second order (calculate by stiffness)		408.71	495.69	548.99

Table 3: Comparison of vibration frequencies of cylindrical shells with different layers

It can be seen that the beam-type vibration frequency of composite cylindrical shell is positively proportional to the axial elastic modulus (E_x). And the stronger the anisotropy of composite material is, the larger the error of calculated value based on the equivalent stiffness model will be. The degree of anisotropy can be expressed by $E_x - E_\theta$ or E_x/E_θ .

Although the beam-type vibration frequency of the cylindrical shell is mainly related to axial stiffness, it should not design the layup angle according to the value of E_x . E_θ can't be too small, and the values of E_x and E_θ need to be coordinated, which makes sense for composite design.

In addition, the Poisson's ratio of isotropic is changed, and the calculation results are shown in the Tab. It can be found that as the influence factor $\sqrt{1 - \nu^2}$ decreases, the first-order and second-order vibration frequencies also decrease. But the two are not in a simple linear relationship. When the Poisson's ratio of the material differs greatly from the 0.3, which is the Poisson's ratio of commonly used materials, the effect on the frequency is not negligible.

Poisson's ratio	F1	Relative Error	F2	Relative Error	$\sqrt{1 - \nu^2}$
0.33	700.17	0	1832.2	0	0.94398
0.1	701.22	+0.15%	1841.0	+0.48%	0.994987
0.2	700.75	+0.083%	1837.1	+0.267%	0.9797959
0.3	700.30	+0.0186%	1933.3	+0.06%	0.9539392
0.4	699.88	-0.0414%	1829.6	-0.1417%	0.916515
0.5	699.52	-0.0928%	1826.3	-0.322%	0.8717224

Table 4: Influence of Poisson's ratio on vibration frequency of cylindrical shell

Design of experiments is adopted, with layup angle of each layer of the composite material as the independent variables, and the design space is $[0^\circ, 90^\circ]$. A total of 450 groups of design points are selected uniformly in the design space using Optimal Latin hypercube design method. According to the above stiffness characteristic conversion relationship, the expected frequency values are calculated and the error values are defined as follows

$$\text{Error1} = \frac{F_{r1} - F_{c1}}{F_{c1}} \times 100\% \quad \text{Error2} = \frac{F_{r2} - F_{c2}}{F_{c2}} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

$E_x - E_\theta$, E_x/E_θ and $\sqrt{1 - \nu_x \cdot \nu_\theta}$ are plotted on the abscissa respectively, Error1 and Error2 are plotted on the ordinate. The influence of each factor on the error is analyzed by curve fitting.

Since the layup angles of the composite material are uniformly selected in the design space, the value range of Poisson's ratio is quite different from that of ordinary isotropic material. However, the influence of Poisson's ratio factor on the frequency error cannot be found intuitively according to the calculated scatter plot. The scatter diagram is shown in Fig 5.

Figure 5: Influence of factor on error of calculated value.

However, when $E_x - E_\theta$ and E_x/E_θ are taken as the abscise respectively and Error as the ordinate, it can be found that the error between the beam-type frequency values calculated based on the equivalent stiffness model of the isotropic material and the frequency values extracted by Abaqus is directly proportional to $E_x - E_\theta$ and E_x/E_θ , which can be approximately expressed by exponential curve.

Figure 6: Influence of $E_x - E_\theta$ on the error of calculated value.

Figure 7: Influence of E_x/E_θ on the error of calculated value.

When $E_x - E_\theta = 0$ or $E_x/E_\theta = 1$, the error is close to 0. Once the acceptable error range is determined, appropriate constraints can be added to the subsequent laminate design to achieve the stiffness design at the initial stage of the fuselage design.

If the stringers structure and the skin structure are laid at the same angle, the E_x of both is the same. Thus, by controlling the axial elastic modulus E_x of the fuselage structure, a suitable fuselage structure can be designed according to a given target frequency value.

4 FUSELAGE STRUCTURE DESIGN AND VERIFICATION

A kind of fuselage structure with variable thickness skin is designed, including 12 Z-shape longerons that are symmetric about the z axis. The section shape is shown in the Fig 8.

Figure 8: Cross-Section of Fuselage & Longeron.

The moment of inertia and area of each section can be expressed as follows

$$\begin{cases} I_x = \sum_{i=1}^n \left\{ \left(\frac{5}{6} + \frac{\cos 2\alpha_i}{2} \right) [(b + \delta)^4 - b^4] + 2(4b + 2\delta)\delta(R \cos \alpha_i)^2 \right\} + \pi t R^3 \\ I_z = \sum_{i=1}^n \left\{ \left(\frac{5}{6} - \frac{\cos 2\alpha_i}{2} \right) [(b + \delta)^4 - b^4] + 2(4b + 2\delta)\delta(R \sin \alpha_i)^2 \right\} + \pi t R^3 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$A = 2\pi R t + 4(4b + 2\delta)\delta$$

Two optimization designs were carried out using the matlab genetic algorithm toolbox. Assuming that the thickness of each layer of the composite material is equal, the angle of the layer is taken as the design parameter, $E_x=70000\text{MPa}$ is taken as the optimization objective, and the value range of E_θ and poisson's ratio is taken as the constraint condition, the angle of each layer of the composite material can be calculated.

It should be noted that the ply angle and thickness calculated here represent the percentage of each ply angle as a percentage of the total thickness. The specific layer thickness and sequence should be designed according to the section shape.

Then, according to the stiffness distribution index K and the composite material elastic modulus E_x calculated above, detailed design parameters of each cross-section can be obtained, such as skin thickness t, fuselage radius R, etc.

The frequency values and position of modal nodes are extracted with ABAQUS, and the comparison results are shown as follows. It can be found that in the case of first-order beam-type vibration, the calculated result is in good accordance with the target value. The error between the calculated result and the target value increases as the frequency increases. It is speculated that due to the linear transitions are adopted between the sections in the equivalent stiffness model and structural design, the stiffness distribution cannot be completely fitted. It can be improved by curve fitting or increasing the number of design surfaces, but it will increase the time cost. This method can meet the needs of engineering design in low-order frequency simulation. It can provide reference for the stiffness design of the composite fuselage

Figure 9: Equivalent stiffness model (left) & fuselage structure (right)

Figure 10: Modal shape of equivalent stiffness model (red) & fuselage structure (black)

Modal Frequency	Target value(cycles/time)	Calculation value(cycles/time)	Relative Error
F7	140	138.49	-1.08%
F8	150	149.91	-0.06%
F10	280	268.90	-3.96%

F11	305	277.73	-8.94%
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Table 5: Comparisons between target & calculated frequency.

Position of Modal Nodes	Target value(mm)	Calculation value(mm)	Relative Error
7S1	920	902	-0.45%
7S2	3080	3098	0.45%
8S1	890	872	-0.45%
8S2	3120	3137	0.43%
10S1	490	495	0.13%
10S2	2000	2010	0.25%
10S3	3510	3514	0.10%
11S1	500	500	0.00%
11S2	1990	2000	0.25%
11S3	3480	3490	0.25%

Table 6: Comparisons between target & calculated modal node position.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

This paper presents a study on a composite fuselage design method based on dynamic stiffness criterion.

a) Equivalent stiffness model of fuselage structure is established based on the stiffness index. The generalized equivalent stiffness reduction model is adopted to effectively increase the calculation speed and ensure the accuracy of results. The equivalent stiffness model is optimized with the node position as the constraint and modal frequency as the optimization objective. Through theoretical analysis, the stiffness conversion relationship between the model and the fuselage structure is deduced. The stiffness value of the fuselage structure on each cross-section can be derived by taking the frequency ratio and the model stiffness as known quantity.

b) Through the theoretical analysis and experimental design, the influence of the parameters of the anisotropic material on the beam-type vibration frequency of the cylindrical shell beam is calculated. It is found that the frequency error has an obvious exponential relationship with $E_x - E_\theta$ and E_x/E_θ . By specifying the error range, the value range of the respective elastic modulus can be constrained, thereby constraining the layup design of the composite material.

c) Based on the equivalent stiffness value, supplemented by the material elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio constraint, the MATLAB genetic algorithm is used to calculate the detailed design parameters of composite material and cross-section of fuselage. For higher precision design requirements, besides adding stiffness index constraint, other design criteria could be considered, such as strength criterion, damage tolerance criterion, etc.

d) A kind of composite fuselage structure is designed and the modal frequency and the modal nodes are extracted. These dynamic stiffness parameters are in good accordance with the parameters of equivalent stiffness model. This method can predict the stiffness index of the fuselage structure, thereby guiding the design of the fuselage structure, especially at the initial design stage.

REFERENCES

- [1] Forsberg K, Axisymmetric and beam-type vibrations of thin cylindrical shells[J], *Aiaa Journal*, 7(2):221-227, 2012.
- [2] Xuebin Li, Free Vibration of Analysis and Comparison Study of Orthotropic Circular Cylindrical Shells, *Ship Science and Technology*, Vol. 24, No. 2, pp 7-14, 2002.
- [3] Flugge. W, *Stresses in Shell*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1960, Chap. 5, pp. 219,220, and 233.